

A novel ionophoretic technique in the study of binary and ternary complexes of nickel(II) and cobalt(II)

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Ionophoretic technique has been used to study the equilibria in simple and mixed ligand systems in solution. For the study of ternary complexes the concentration of serine is kept constant, while that of a secondary ligand nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) is varied. A graph of mobility against $-\log [\text{NTA}]$ is used to obtain information on the formation of mixed ligand complexes and to calculate the stability constants.

In the present communication an effort has been made to assess the stability constants of metal complexes with a single ligand along with the systematic study of ternary complexes formed in a system containing various electrolyte ingredients. A simple ionophoretic tube¹ has been designed for this work, which yields better results after standardization.

Results and discussion

M-serine system :

The overall mobility (U) is a composite parameter contributed by different ionic species of the metal ion and is given by the following equation :

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1 k_1 [L] + u_2 k_1 k_2 [L]^2 + \dots}{1 + k_1 [L] + k_1 k_2 [L]^2 + \dots}$$

where k 's are the stability constants of complexes and $[L]$ is the concentration of serinate anion; u 's are the ionic mobilities of different species of the metal ions which can be assessed from the plateaus, of the figure. In the region between first and second plateau, the system contains overwhelmingly a mixture of free metal ion and 1 : 1 complex. From Fig. 1 it is evident that there is no formation of 1 : 2 complex, hence the third term in the numerator and the denominator of the above equation can be justifiably neglected. U would be equal to $u_0 + u_1/2$, provided $k_1[L] = 1$. Accordingly, the pH corresponding to the average value of u_0 and u_1 is found from the figure. With the knowledge of the dissociation constants of serine ($pK_2 = 9.06$, $pK_1 = 2.13$)², the concentration of serinate ion at this pH is calculated. Its reciprocal gives the stability constants k of the 1 : 1 complex. The calculated values are given in Table 1.

M-NTA system :

The overall mobilities of the metal ions in solution in

the presence of NTA at different pH values are represented in Fig. 2. It is evident from the figure that with each metal ion two plateaus are formed. The mobility of the second plateau lies in the negative region, which shows the negatively charged nature of the complex. Hence, only one NTA anion is assumed to combine with one bivalent metal ion to give a 1 : 1 M-NTA complex which is in conformity with finding of the other workers.³ The stability constants of complexes with NTA (k_{M-NTA}^M) were calculated as described for the M-serine system and are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Stability constants of some binary and ternary complexes of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} with serine and NTA

Ionic strength = 0.1 M, Temp. = 25°

Stability constant	Ni ^{II} value		Co ^{II} value	
	Calcd.	Lit.*	Calcd.	Lit.*
$\log k_{M-serine}^M$	7.32	5.45	6.81	4.36
$\log k_{M-NTA}^M$	9.66	11.50	9.47	10.38
$\log k_{M-serine-NTA}^M$	5.91	—	5.88	—

*Ref. 2.

M-serine-NTA system :

This system was studied at pH 7 with a specific purpose. It was observed from the mobility curves for M-serine and M-NTA binary systems that binary complexes (M-serine) and (M-NTA) are formed much before pH 7. To avoid any side-interactions the transformation of the M-serine complexes into M-serine-NTA complexes is investigated at pH 7.0.

The plots of overall mobility (absorbance difference) against $-\log [\text{NTA}]$ are given in Fig. 3 which shows two plateaus. The positive mobility in the region of the first plateau is obviously due to 1 : 1 M-serine complexes (ML*) (see Fig. 1). The mobility corresponding to the second plateau lies in the negative region which shows the negatively

Fig. 1. Mobility curves : (◆) Ni^{II}-serine system, (⊗) Co^{II}-serine system.

charged nature of the complex. However, the mobility for the last plateau is not in agreement with the mobility of 1 : 1 M-NTA complex (Fig. 2). It is therefore inferred that the species corresponding to the second plateau is due to

Fig. 2. Mobility curves : (◆) Ni^{II}-NTA system, (⊗) Co^{II}-NTA system.

the coordination of NTA³⁻ anion to a 1 : 1 M-serinate moiety resulting the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 (M-serine-NTA)²⁻ mixed complex. This can be shown as

$$U = u_0 fM\text{-serine} + u_1 fM\text{-serine-NTA} \quad (4)$$

where u_0 and u_1 are the mobilities and $fM\text{-serine}$ and $fM\text{-serine-NTA}$ are the mole fractions of M-serine and M-serine-NTA complexes, respectively. From Fig. 3 the total concentration of NTA at which the overall mobility is mean of the mobilities of the two plateaus was determined. For this the concentration of the NTA³⁻ anion at pH 7.0 was calculated. $K_{M\text{-serine-NTA}}^{M\text{-serine}}$ is obviously equal to $1/[L]$. These calculated values of stability constants are also recorded in Table 1.

Fig. 3. Mobility curves : (◆) Ni^{II}-serine-NTA system, (⊗) Co^{II}-serine-NTA system.

Experimental

The technique consisted in carrying electrophoresis in background electrolyte containing 0.1 M perchloric acid and 0.01 M serine/0.2 × 10⁻² M NTA with metal ions Ni^{II} and Co^{II} and NaOH was added to produce the desired pH for the study of binary complexes. In each electrophoretic observations electrolysis was carried out for 45 min at 50 V at 25°.

For the study of ternary complexes, the experimental procedure was slightly modified. Here the background electrolyte contained secondary ligand (NTA) in addition to primary ligand (serine). For the ternary complexes the pH was always maintained at 7 (by adding NaOH solution) and the concentration of secondary ligand (NTA) ranged from 10⁻⁶ to 10⁻² M.

Procedure for binary complexes : A set of 15 ml solution containing 1 × 10⁻³ M Ni^{II}/Co^{II}, 0.1 M HClO₄ and 1 × 10⁻² serine was prepared at different pH values. A 10 ml of the solution was taken in an electrophoretic tube and thermostated at 25°. The tube (18 cm × 5 mm dia) was adjusted in such a way that the level of the solution in one wide end arm reached a circular mark on it. This adjustment fixed the volume of the solution on both sides of the middle stopper. Two (0.5 cm × 0.5 cm) platinum electrodes were dipped in each arm cup and 50 V potential difference was applied between them. Electrolysis of the solution was allowed for 45 min after which the middle stopper of the tube was closed. The solution of the anodic compartment was taken in a 15 ml flask. The nickel content of the solution was converted to nickel dimethyl glyoximate complex⁴. The volume was raised up to the mark and the absorbance was measured at 445 nm with CZ-Specol spectrophotometer. The Co^{II} content of the anodic compartment was converted

to Co^{II}-thiocyanate complex⁴ and absorbance was measured at 625 nm after making up the volume to 15 ml.

Procedure for the study of ternary complexes : An appropriate reaction mixture containing metal ions and serine and 0.1 M perchloric acid was adjusted to pH 7.0 and the secondary ligand was added progressively and the ionophoretic mobility recorded. The mobility was plotted against $-\log [\text{NTA}]$.

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References

1. R. K. P. Singh and K. L. Yadava, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1986, **35**, 77.
2. A. E. Martell and R. M. Smith, "Critical Stability Constants, Vol. 1 : Amino Acids", 1994.
3. T. R. Bhat, R. R. Das and J. Shanker, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 324; O. K. Borggaard, O. Farver and V. S. Anderson, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1971, **25**, 3541; J. Israeli, J. R. Coyouette and R. Volpe, *Talanta*, 1971, **18**, 737; D. Hopgood and R. J. Angelici, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 2508.
4. A. I. Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 5th. ed., ELBS, London, 2001.